

SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS OF BAMBOO ARTISANS IN AMRAVATI DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

The present investigation conducted explores the lives and challenges of traditional bamboo artisans. A sample families of 60 artisans from areas like Dharni, Bihali and Anjangaon of Amravati district was selected, and data was compiled using a structured questionnaire. Most of these artisans come from Scheduled Tribe families and have been involved in bamboo profession for generations. They mainly use two local bamboo species viz. *Dendrocalamus stocksii* (Manga) and *Bambusa arundinacea* (Katang) to make 9 to 10 types of traditional products. Analyzed data revealed that most artisans are middle-aged, only 39 percent of artisans have completed their junior high school. The average earning of artisans between ₹10,000 to ₹20,000 per year from bamboo profession, which is major source of income but their overall socio-economic status has low. Because of less planning and accessible market, artisans used to sell products through wholesalers. They face several problems, like outdated tools, pests, lack of skilled workers, limited finances, and inconsistent demand which make it hard for artisans to grow their business. However, bamboo-based crafts offer both income and environmental benefits. Proper support, such as training, better market access, and government help, this sector could create more jobs and promote sustainable development of this profession. This finding highlights the need for targeted efforts to improve the livelihoods of bamboo artisans while preserving this valuable traditional craft.

Keywords: artisans, katang, livelihood, marketing, socio-economic.

Introduction

Bamboo represents the most diverse group of plants within the grass family (Poaceae), specifically belonging to the subfamily *Bambusoideae*, considered one of its most primitive lineages. In India, bamboo is distributed across diverse ecological zones, from sea level up to altitudes of 3,600 meters, with optimal growth conditions found between 770 and 1,080 meters above sea level. Bamboos are present in almost all Indian states, with the exception of the Kashmir region in Jammu and Kashmir (Salil Telwir, 2019).

As a natural resource, bamboo is strong, versatile, and highly renewable, earning it numerous titles such as “Green Gold,” “Poor Man’s Timber,” and “Cradle to Coffin Timber.” (Dhurga, 2013). Its uses span across various sectors including agriculture, construction, cottage industries, and environmental protection. Bamboo serves as a source for fodder, fuel, timber, pulp, edible shoots, and raw material for furniture and handicrafts. It is increasingly being used in the manufacture of decorative plywood, composite boards, roofing sheets, and even earthquake-resistant housing. Bamboo also contributes significantly to rural livelihoods and local economies while providing critical ecological services such as soil erosion control, streambank stabilization, and enhancement of soil quality (Janssen, 2000).

Bamboo has historical and cultural significance, being used for millennia in daily life from cradles to coffins. Archaeological evidence indicates bamboo baskets were in use as far back as 7,000 years ago. Over time, its utility expanded to construction, tools, furniture, musical instruments, and weapons. During the Industrial Revolution and both World Wars, bamboo played key roles in packaging, supply transport, and communication. Today, it continues to support various levels of production from household and farm use to industrial and medicinal applications and remains central to India’s traditional cottage industries (Kalanzi *et.al*, 2017)

Table 1: Details of studied sites in Amravati district of Maharashtra.

District	Studied Area	Latitude	Longitude
Amravati (Maharashtra State)	Dharni	21.53 ⁰ N	77.56 ⁰ E
	Bihali	21.39 ⁰ N	77.46 ⁰ E
	Anjangaon Surji	21.17 ⁰ N	77.31 ⁰ E

According to the International Bamboo and Rattan Organization (INBAR, 2019), the global bamboo trade was valued at USD 68.8 billion in 2018, impacting 2.5 billion people directly or indirectly. China alone accounted for 67% of the world’s bamboo exports, generating USD 2.2 billion in export revenue. Although India possesses a larger bamboo resource base (15 million hectares) than China — with major bamboo-bearing areas in Madhya Pradesh (1.84 m ha), Arunachal Pradesh (1.57 m ha), Maharashtra (1.35 m ha), and Odisha (1.12 m ha) it remains a net importer of bamboo. The National Bamboo Mission estimates India’s annual bamboo production at 14.6 million tonnes, with yields ranging from 1 to 3 tonnes per hectare. In 2020–2021 (April–November), India exported bamboo products worth USD 140.47 million while importing USD 107 million, indicating considerable potential for growth through improved production systems and value chain development (KFRI, 2022).

In light of bamboo’s ecological, economic, and cultural significance, as well as its vast potential in climate mitigation and sustainable development, strategic research and policy interventions are essential to enhance productivity, value addition, and market competitiveness.

Materials and Methods

For the present study the research methodology viz. qualitative and quantitative techniques in research were accepted.

The research methodology adopted under following heads: -

1. Details of studied site
2. Sampling procedure
3. Statistical Analysis

The study was conducted in Amravati District of Maharashtra state during 2024-25. As per the map showing surveyed locations which lies between latitude 20⁰55’33” North and 77⁰45’33” South. The climatic condition of Amravati district lies between tropical wet to dry characterized by high temperature.

Details of studied site

Sampling Procedure

Keeping in view the objectives of the study, purposive stratified random sampling technique was adopted. Total 3 location were selected then from each location total 20 respondent artisans families were selected; total 60 respondent were interviewed and information gathered and documented.

The data was collected personally by face-to-face interactions. Primary data was collected through a structured interview schedule. The secondary data was collected from various books, journals, government portals, websites relevant to the investigation interest and documented systematically. Artisans were interviewed through personal interview. Prior to interview, the artisans were taken into confidence by revealing the actual purpose of the study and also full care was taken to develop good rapport with them. The interview was conducted in the most formal and friendly atmosphere without any complications.

Statistical analysis

All the variables of the study were categorized using scores and the analysis was done by using simple statistical method and correlation study were done of dependent variables to draw the interference and conclusion which was discussed here.

Results and Discussions

Table 2 revealed the detail status of the bamboo artisans based on various demographic, socio-economic, and occupational factors. In terms of caste, the majority of artisans belongs to the Scheduled Tribe (ST) category, comprising 66 percent (40 individuals), while 34 percent (20 individuals) were from the Scheduled Caste (SC) category. In age distribution, most artisans were in the middle-age group (25–50 years), making up 55 percent (33 individuals). About 45 percent (27 individuals) were older than 50 years, and only no artisans were in the young age group (up to 25 years).

Regarding gender, a large majority were male 62 percent, (37 individuals), while 38 percent (23 individuals) were female. In terms of education, 18 percent (11 individuals) were uneducated. Among the educated, 21 percent (13 individuals) had primary education (classes 1–5), 39 percent (23 individuals) had studied up to junior high school (classes 5–8), and 13 percent (8 individuals) had completed high school

(classes 9–10). A smaller proportion had studied up to intermediate 9 percent, (5 individuals), while no artisans had completed graduation and post-graduation. Marital status showed that the majority of artisans (99 percent, 59 individuals) were married. Only 1 percent (1 individuals) were unmarried, and none were widowed. For family size, 45 percent (27 households) had small families (up to 5 members), 42 percent (25 households) had medium-sized families (6–8 members), and 13 percent (8 households) had large families (more than 8 members).

In terms of family type, most artisans (78 percent, 47 individuals) belonged to nuclear families, while 22 percent (13 individuals) lived in joint families. When considering work experience, none of the artisans reported having no experience and low experience, 43 percent (26 individuals) had medium experience (6–10 years), and the majority (57 percent, 34 individuals) had high experience (11–15 years). Whereas with respect to occupation, 34 percent (20 individuals) were engaged only in bamboo-related activities, while a vast majority (66 percent, 40 individuals) combined farming with bamboo work. None of the respondents were engaged in farming alone. While, on the basis of income from bamboo activity, most artisans i.e. 100 percent, (60 individuals) earned a low income (₹10,000–₹20,000 per year).

Similar study was performed by Kumar (2009), studied on conservation of Ringal (a dwarf bamboo) through economic development in Rudraprayag district. His study revealed that Schedule caste families were highly involved in Ringal based livelihood activities.

Rana *et.al* (2009) studied the economics and employment generation trade of bamboo-based products in Eastern Bangladesh and obtained reliable information about their status and socio-economic significance.

Sundriyal and Sundriyal (2011) conducted their case study of traditional artisans of Uttarakhand state, there study revealed that 65 percent of the families earned an average income of Rs.2000-4000 per month. Anita Kumari (2019) studied on socio-economic status of forest-based rural artisans in mid-hill zone of Himachal Pradesh and concluded that the rural artisans activities are seasonal and not much profitable which provides short term employment.

Table 2 : Detail status of artisans according to the various variables. (n = 60)

Variables	Categories	Locations			Frequency (n =60)	Percentage (%)
		Dharni	Bihali	Anjangaon		
Caste / category	SC	0	0	20	20	34
	ST	20	20	0	40	66
Age distribution (in years)	Young (upto 25)	0	0	0	0	0
	Middle (25-50)	2	16	15	33	55
	Old(51-above)	18	4	5	27	45
Gender	Male	15	16	6	37	62
	Female	5	4	14	23	38
Education status	Uneducated	1	7	3	11	18

	Primary Education (1-5)	5	5	3	13	21
	Junior Highschool (5-8)	7	6	10	23	39
	Highschool (9-10)	3	1	4	8	13
	Intermediate (11-12)	4	1	0	5	9
	Graduation	0	0	0	0	0
	Post Graduation	0	0	0	0	0
Marital Status	Married	19	20	20	59	99
	Unmarried	1	0	0	1	1
	Widow	0	0	0	0	0
Family size	Small (Upto 5 members)	6	7	14	27	45
	Medium (6-8)	7	12	6	25	42
	Large (above 8)	7	1	0	8	13
Family Type	Nuclear	7	20	20	47	78
	Joint	13	0	0	13	22
Work Experience	No Experience	0	0	0	0	0
	Low experience (1-5 yrs)	0	0	0	0	0
	Medium experience (6-10)	10	16	0	26	43
	High Experience (11-15)	10	4	20	34	57
Occupation	Farming	0	0	0	0	0
	Bamboo activity	20	0	0	20	34
	Farming + bamboo activity	0	20	20	40	66
Income from bamboo activity	Low (10,000-20,000)	20	20	20	60	100
	Medium (20,000-30,000)	0	0	0	0	0
	High (30,000-40,000)	0	0	0	0	0

Table 3: Status of marketing channels adapted by artisans in Amravati District. (n=60).

Marketing channels	Frequency (n=60)	Percentage (%)
Channel I (Artisans to Consumers)	18	30
Channel II (Artisans to retailers to consumers)	14	24
Channel III (Artisans to wholesalers to consumers)	28	46

Fig 2: Various marketing channels adapted by artisans.

Table 3 revealed the status of artisans based on the marketing channels they use to sell their bamboo products. Among the 60 respondents, the majority 46 percent (28 artisans) followed by Channel III, where they sell their products through wholesalers before reaching consumers. This method may offer artisans bulk sales and reduced marketing efforts, but it often involves the lowest price realization for their products. Whereas, 24 percent (14 artisans) use Channel II, where products pass through retailers before reaching the final consumer. This approach may be more convenient for artisans, but it often results in lower returns due to the involvement of intermediaries who take a share of the profit.

While 30 percent (18 individuals) use Channel I, in which artisans sell their products directly to consumers. This direct-to-consumer model may help artisans earn higher profit margins by eliminating middlemen, although it requires greater market access, time investment, and selling skills.

Similarly, Gogoi (2020), had studied on Market analysis of bamboo products in Assam. He found that there is wide variation in marketing channels adopted for selling bamboo products from area to area. Small bamboo growers directly market their products while others sell directly to retailers. But majorly the bamboo products were sold to traders and commission agents who then sell it further to the

wholesalers. Thus, number of marketing channels were observed in the study area. The common marketing channel that exists in the area were-

Channel II – Artisans to wholesalers to retailers to consumers.
Channel III – Artisans to Middleman to wholesalers to retailers to consumers.

Table 4: Study of constraints faced by artisans in Amravati district.

Sr. No	Constraints faced by artisans	No. of Artisans	Percentage responses to constraints	Rank
1	Lack of modern tools, equipment, and knowledge about pests and diseases	60	100	I
2	Pest and disease issues while production	60	100	I
3	Labour shortages	60	100	I
4	Sales difficulties: cash payment and bargaining problems	60	100	I
5	Poor market access: lack of information and trader connections	42	70	II
6	Market conditions: high marketing cost, glut in post-harvest, forced low-price sales due to poor storage	42	70	II
7	Capital limitations for product promotion	42	70	II
8	Environmental and wildlife-related challenges	20	34	III
9	Lack of access of raw materials and transportation	0	0	IV
10	Price and input cost instability	0	0	IV

The table 4 shows that most of the artisans encountered a number of challenges to continue with their business. The bamboo-based artisans encounter multiple challenges that hinder their productivity, profitability, and market access. Identifying these constraints is essential for formulating effective interventions and policy recommendations. The major constraints faced by artisans, as derived from the study, are summarized in Table 4

The constraints are ranked based on their prevalence. The most frequently cited constraints, reported by 100 percent of the respondents (60 artisans), include the lack of modern tools, equipment, and pest/disease knowledge; pest and disease issues during production; labour shortages; and sales difficulties such as problems with cash payments and bargaining. These constraints were all ranked as Rank I. The second-highest ranked issues (Rank II), identified by 70 percent of respondents (42 artisans), include poor market access due to lack of information and trader connections, adverse market conditions (e.g., high marketing costs and forced low-price sales due to poor storage), and limited capital for product promotion.

Environmental and wildlife-related challenges were reported by only 34 percent (20 artisans), thus receiving a Rank III.

The least significant constraints, with no artisans citing them (0), were lack of access to raw materials and transportation, as well as price and input cost instability; these were assigned Rank IV.

Similarly, Ghimire (2008) studied on an assessment of the dependency of farmers on bamboo resources for rural livelihood in Lalitpur district, Nepal reported that the lack of market, bamboo raw material, and technical knowledge about bamboo plantation and management and skill development trainings, small land holding, subsidies and micro-finance from the government are major constraints of bamboo craft making in the study area.

Correlation Analysis

Table 5 depicted the Pearson correlation coefficients among key variables related to community demographics, socioeconomic status, and bamboo income. The strength and direction of the relationships are categorized as strong, moderate, or weak, and as positive or negative. A strong positive correlation found between Occupation and Marketing Channels ($r = 0.6325$)** indicates that individuals engaged in certain occupations are more likely to utilize or have access to marketing channels for bamboo products. A moderate positive relationship in Education and Income from Bamboo ($r = 0.2571$) suggests that individuals with higher education tend to earn slightly more from bamboo-based activities. Family Size and Income from Bamboo ($r = 0.2466$) shows a moderate positive correlation implies that larger family sizes may contribute more labour or support, resulting in higher bamboo income. Work Experience and Education ($r = 0.1639$) shows

weak positive linkage shows a slight trend that more experienced individuals also have higher education levels.

A very strong negative correlation found in family type and occupation ($r = -0.8771$) indicates that different family types are associated with distinctly different occupational patterns. A strong negative correlation in Community and Work Experience ($r = -0.6183$) suggests that individuals with more work experience are less represented in certain communities. Community and Gender ($r = -0.4605$) shows a moderate to strong negative correlation points to gender disparities in community representation. Age and Education ($r = -0.5605$) shows moderate negative relationship reveals that younger individuals tend to have higher levels of education. Marketing Channels and Education ($r = -0.2956$) had moderate negative correlation suggests that more educated individuals may rely less on traditional marketing channels. Marketing Channels and Family Type ($r = -0.5547$) had moderate to strong negative relationship implies that some family structures are less likely to engage with certain marketing channels.

Conclusion

A field study during course of it is observed that there is great potential for bamboo artisans in the Amravati District, especially among Scheduled Tribe families in Dharni and Bihali. These families have deep traditional knowledge of bamboo craftsmanship. The most commonly used bamboo types are *Dendrocalamus stocksii* and *Bambusa arundinaceae*, locally known as *Manga* and *Katang*, which they use to make a variety of traditional items.

Most of the artisans were found to be middle-aged, while younger people were not involved. Since the younger generation is often more open to learning and experimenting with new designs, encouraging their participation is important. Education levels among artisans were also low only 39 percent had completed junior high school, so offering both formal and informal education could help improve their skills and awareness.

All of the artisans earn between Rs. 10,000 to 20,000 a month from their bamboo work, which plays a vital role in supporting their families. Despite this, their overall economic condition remains poor. They usually make 9 to 10 different bamboo products that are in local demand and sell them, using both direct and indirect methods. However, they need more support to reach larger markets. The study revealed that the marketing channel III (Artisans to wholesaler to consumer) is helpful for the artisans to sale their products. Training programs and better market connections could help expand their work. The artisans face several challenges: outdated tools, pest problems, not enough labour, cash issues, and irregular demand for their products. Even so, bamboo work is eco-friendly and helps the environment, making it especially important in times of climate change. With the right government support, this craft can be strengthened, improving the

livelihoods of these artisans and boosting the bamboo industry in Maharashtra.

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Table 5 : Correlation coefficient values for the variables.

	Community	Age	Gender	Education	Marital Status	Family Size	Family Type	Work Experience	Occupation	Income Bamboo	Marketing Channels
Community	1										
Age	-0.228851827	1									
Gender	-0.460546857	-0.14007	1								
Education	-0.020389065	-0.56051	0.193239	1							
Marital Status	0.092057462	-0.35288	0.165124	0.257144	1						
Family Size	0.389998599	0.070819	-0.18331	0.11651	0.05931681	1					
Family Type	0.277350098	-0.23009	-0.10756	0.096133	-0.0510643	0.249252	1				
Work Experience	-0.618346942	0.084362	0.136048	0.163898	-0.1488767	-0.15647	0.145114	1			
Occupation	-0.316227766	0.2352	0.168633	-0.10961	0.05822225	-0.20376	-0.87706	-0.1203314	1		
Income Bamboo	0.092057462	-0.03687	0.165124	0.257144	-0.0169492	0.246633	-0.05106	-0.1488767	0.0582223	1	
Marketing Channels	-0.5	0.371884	0.193914	-0.29564	-0.1841149	-0.37304	-0.5547	0.0951303	0.6324555**	-0.18411	1

(** indicates the strongly positive correlation)